

THE ENERGY-ABSORBING CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITE TUBE-REINFORCED ALUMINUM FOAMS UNDER COMPRESSION

Zheng. Liu¹, Dawei. Ma¹, Zhongling Zhu¹, and Zhendong. Zhang¹

¹School of mechanical engineering, Nanjing University of Science and Technology, Nanjing, China, 1169890977@qq.com

Keywords: CFRE fiber, Aluminum foams, Compression test, Energy absorption

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the energy-absorbing characteristics of the combination of two lightweight material—carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CFRE) tubes and aluminium foams. Initial axial quasi-static compression tests are undertaken on five types of CFRE tubes with different wall thicknesses and internal diameters in order to establish the influencing factors of the specific energy absorption (SEA) and obtain the most efficient value of the ratio of internal diameter to thickness (D/t). The result shows that the energy absorbed during compression increases with the values of D/t while the SEA maximizes at D/t equals 13 when the external diameter is constant. Then a series compression tests are conducted on the aluminum foams containing embedded CFRE tubes in order to characterize the energy-absorbing ability of these materials and seek the best combination and configuration of them. The response indicates that in the case of the same thickness of CFRE tubes, with the increase of the number of CFRE tubes, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase, and the length of the platform decreases. When the numbers of CFRE tubes are same, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase with the increase of the thickness of CFRP tubes, and the length of the platform decreases. The SEA of CFRE tubes is higher than that of aluminum foam, so the SEA can be effectively improved by inserting CFRE tubes into aluminum foam material. However, at the same time, they also increase the stress level during deformation. In the concrete design of protection structure, considering the protecting and economic requirements comprehensively, the aluminum foam material with lower stress level should be used as far as possible while the use of CFRE tubes should be controlled in a reasonable range.

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy-absorbing materials have been a significant topic in the field of buffering protection in recent years. Extensive testing on various types of structure and material shows that composite materials can provide outstanding energy-absorbing characteristics [1-10]. For example, in a detailed investigation of energy-absorption in composite structures, Jacob et al. [1] determined that only 0.66 kg of a high-performance thermoplastic matrix composite is required to absorb the energy of a 1000 kg car travelling at 15.5 m/s. Published values for the SEA of widely-used composites, such as carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, generally fall in the range 50–80 kJ/kg [2,3], but can be as high as 110 kJ/kg [4].

A number of researchers have studied the influence on energy absorption of tube geometry [7–9]. Thornton and Edwards concluded that for a given fibre stacking sequence, carbon, glass and Kevlar fibre reinforced circular tubes outperform their square and rectangular counterparts [7]. Mamalis et al. [8] investigated the crushing characteristics of a range of glass fibre reinforced composite structures with circular, square and conical cross-sections and found that circular tubes offered the highest values of energy-absorption. Farley [10] investigated the influence of specimen size on the energy-absorbing capability of carbon and Kevlar reinforced epoxy cylindrical tubes and observed that the ratio of the inner diameter of the tube to that of its thickness (D/t), greatly influences the specific crushing stress of the tube.

Aluminum foams and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (CFRE) tubes are two lightweight materials with high strength, stiffness and capability of energy absorption. Some investigators have performed a series of studies on them respectively and comprehensively [12-22]. Cheng [12] investigated the compressive deformation behavior and energy absorption characteristic of aluminum foam with elastic filler and found that the energy absorption efficiency of the open-cell aluminum foam filled with silicate rubber (AFFSR) maintains a high level (above 0.6) over a wide strain range from 3% to 60%. R.A. Alia [25] investigated the energy-absorbing characteristics of polymer foams reinforced with small carbon fibre reinforced epoxy tubes and found that the energy-absorbing characteristics of these systems exceed values associated with other core materials, such as aluminium honeycombs, polymer honeycombs and metal foams.

This paper investigates the energy-absorbing characteristics of the combination of two lightweight material — carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CFRE) tubes and aluminium foams. Quasi-static compression tests were undertaken on five types of CFRE tubes and the aluminum foams containing embedded CFRE tubes in order to characterize the energy-absorbing ability of these materials and seek the best combination and configuration of them. The results would help the development of composite material in buffering protection industry.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Constituent materials

The composite materials investigated in this study were based on CFRE tubes supplied by Nanjing Chenmao Corporation and aluminum foams supplied by Suzhou Fangdou Corporation.

Toray T700 carbon fibre prepreg was selected to manufacture into tubes with a $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ stacking sequence oriented along the length of the tube due to its high modulus. Initially, in order to investigate the influencing factors of SEA and seek the most efficient combination of CFRE tubes and aluminum foams, five types of CFRE tubes with different values of the ratio of internal diameter to thickness (D/t) ranging from 4.0 to 28.0 were processed into segments with a length of 30mm, as shown in Figure 1. The external diameter of all the CFRE tubes is 15 mm. The specific parameters are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: Samples of processed 30 mm-long CFRE tubes.

Sample ID	Internal diameter, D (mm)	Thickness, t (mm)	D/t	Mass (g)	Energy absorbed (J)	SEA (kJ/kg)
T1	10	2.5	4.0	4.45	324.87	73.00
T2	11	2.0	5.5	3.78	245.75	65.01
T3	12	1.5	8.0	2.86	182.48	63.80
T4	13	1.0	13.0	2.03	161.73	79.67
T5	14	0.5	28.0	1.11	63.04	56.79

Table 1: Summary of the geometrical and SEA characteristics of 30 mm-long CFRE tubes.

The aluminum foams were processed into plates with a surface size of 120×120 mm and thickness of 30 mm. In order to insert CFRE tubes, 16 mm diameter perforated circular holes were drilled in the

aluminum foam plates. Tubes embedded in aluminum foams samples were arranged as evenly as possible, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: The positioning of the tubes in multi-tube samples.

In order to investigate the influencing factors of the specific energy absorption, aluminum foams samples with different type and different number of CFRE tubes were prepared. Specific parameters are shown in Table 2, and samples of aluminum foams filled with CFRE tubes are seen in Figure 3.

Sample ID	CFRE tube ID	Number of tubes	Mass(g)	Energy absorbed (J)	SEA (kJ/kg)
<i>P1</i>	—	0	234.51	1265.43	5.40
<i>P2</i>	<i>T1</i>	3	220.63	1665.92	7.55
<i>P3</i>	<i>T1</i>	5	242.43	2262.67	9.33
<i>P4</i>	<i>T1</i>	7	251.11	2693.89	10.73
<i>P5</i>	<i>T2</i>	7	224.29	2219.10	9.89
<i>P6</i>	<i>T3</i>	7	201.34	1810.60	8.99
<i>P7</i>	<i>T4</i>	7	237.39	1776.96	7.48
<i>P8</i>	<i>T5</i>	7	224.42	1116.33	4.97
<i>P9</i>	—	—	221.47	697.73	3.15

Table 2: Summary of the geometrical and SEA characteristics of aluminum foams filled with CFRE tubes

P1

P2

P3

Figure 3: Samples of aluminum foams filled with CFRE tubes.

2.3 Quasi-static compression test

The compression tests were conducted in the mechanics laboratory of Nanjing university of science and technology. At room temperature, the specimens were compressed in a universal material tester, maximum pressure of which is up to 30 kN. The samples were placed between two circular steel plattens and compressed at a crosshead until the densification threshold was just exceeded. Due to the large size of the aluminum foam specimen, in order to ensure the uniform force on the acting surface of the specimen, two piece of smooth steel plate with a thickness of about 15mm is placed above and below the specimen. While the CFRE tubes were placed directly on the laboratory bench, without the need for additional devices. The experimental apparatus and methods are seen in Figure 4.

The tests were undertaken at a crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min and interrupted when the crosshead had travelled at least 20 mm. Load and displacement of crosshead were recorded by the sensor of testing machine. The specific energy absorption (SEA) of the samples was determined from the energy under the load–displacement trace and the initial mass of the specimen.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: The positioning of the tubes in multi-tube samples.

Initial axial quasi-static compression tests were undertaken on five types of CFRE tubes with different wall thicknesses and internal diameters in order to ascertain which type of tube with values of the ratio of internal diameter to thickness (D/t) would represent the most effective energy-absorbing reinforcement. Then a series compression tests are conducted on the aluminum foams containing embedded CFRE tubes in order to characterize the energy-absorbing ability of these materials and seek the best combination and configuration of them. The energy absorbed and the SEA were taken focus on in particular and considered as crucial factor to evaluate the energy-absorbing characteristics.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compression tests on the CFRE tubes

The initial part of this study focused on investigating the crush behavior of the individual composite tubes and assessing the influence of the tube diameter to thickness (D/t ratio) on their energy-absorbing capability.

Figure 5 shows the remnants of compressed five different types of CFRE tube samples. An examination of the figure highlights the similar failure mode in the five specimens. The compressive load destabilized the 90° layers and they failed by fragmentation mode, marked with 'I' or 'T' in Figure 5(b) in which layers experience several short-length matrix fractures due to transverse shearing or sharp bending[22]. Closer inspection suggested that the failure process generated a significant number of small fragments, suggesting that a large number of fibres had been fractured during the crush process.

Figure 5: The compressed CFRE tube samples.

Figure 6: Typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on tubes with different values of D/t .

Figure 6 shows typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on tubes with different values of D/t . All five traces exhibited similar characteristics, with failure occurring in a stable manner at an approximately constant force after an initial peak due to the lack of trigger mechanisms. Table 1 indicates that the energy absorbed during compression increased with the values of D/t . Specimen T4 had the highest SEA and T1 came in second, while T1 absorbed twice as much energy as T4 did. Consider the total energy and SEA factors comprehensively, T1 would possess the most efficient energy-absorbing ability.

3.2 Compression tests on the tube-reinforced aluminum foams

The next stage of this research study investigated the behavior of the composite tubes when embedded in aluminum foams. Assess the influence of the tube numbers and value of D/t ratio on the energy-absorbing capability of the combined material.

Figure 7 shows the remnants of compressed aluminum foams filled with CFRE tubes samples. It indicated that the samples were basically compacted. On one hand, the boreholes in aluminum foams were choked up with crashed CFRE tubes so that the compression could not proceed because of the steeply rising stress. The thicker the thickness of the tube, the sooner the interruption of crosshead happened. On the other hand, pure aluminum foams with no inserted tubes were completely compacted into disintegrating slag under a lower level of stress.

Figure 8 shows the typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on aluminum foams filled with tubes. According to Figure 8a, in the case of the same thickness of CFRE tubes, with the increase of the number of CFRE tubes, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the specimen increased, and the length of the platform decreased. When the numbers of CFRE tubes were same, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the specimen increased with the increase of the thickness of CFRE tubes, and the length of the platform decreased, as shown in Figure 8b. Table 2 indicates that specimen P4 had the highest SEA, which possessed the maximum number and thickness of the CFRE tubes. The SEA of CFRP tube was much higher than that of aluminum foam, so the SEA can be effectively improved by inserting CFRP tubes into aluminum foam material.

Figure 7: The compressed aluminum foams filled with CFRE tubes.

Figure 8: Typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on aluminum foams filled with tubes.

3.3 Comparison of SEA of materials

In this investigation, the SEA values of CFRE tubes varies from 56.8 to 79.7 kJ/kg, and the SEA values of aluminum foams were enhanced from 3.2 kJ/kg to 10.7 kJ/kg. Other materials were studied in various researches. Heimbs [27] reported SEA values of a range of honeycombs, foams and other types of lightweight core. It indicated that values of honeycomb-type structures varied from approximately 8 to 45 kJ/kg. Values of polymer foams varied from approximately 1.5 kJ/kg for a polyethylene system to 18 kJ/kg for a high density PMI foam. Additionally Heimbs quoted data from tests on a number of carbon and Kevlar-based foldcore structures, where energy absorption values between 2 and 22.5 kJ/kg were noted [27]. Airoidi et al. [28] manufactured and tested chiral honeycomb structures based on a [0,±45] carbon fibre reinforced plastic and reported values as high as 96.5 kJ/kg. Observation of the chiral structures during failure identified the development of a progressive crushing mode similar to that observed here during tests on plain composite tubes. Although these values for SEA are clearly impressive, it is likely that the cost associated with producing these elegant, if somewhat complex structures, would be significant, potentially outweighing their attractive energy-absorbing characteristics.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A novel tube-reinforced plane structure has been developed in which CFRE tubes are embedded in aluminum foams with low density. Initial tests on CFRE tubes shows that the energy absorbed during compression increases with the values of D/t while the SEA maximizes at D/t equals 13 when the external diameter is constant. Then a series compression tests on the aluminum foams containing embedded CFRE tubes indicates that in the case of the same thickness of CFRE tubes, with the increase of the number of CFRE tubes, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase, and the length of the platform decreases. When the numbers of CFRE tubes are same, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase with the increase of the thickness of CFRP tubes, and the length of the platform decreases.

The SEA of CFRE tubes is much higher than that of aluminum foam, so the SEA can be effectively improved by inserting CFRE tubes into aluminum foam material. However, at the same time, they also increase the stress level during deformation. In the concrete design of protection structure, considering the protecting and economic requirements comprehensively, the aluminum foam material with lower stress level should be used as far as possible while the use of CFRE tubes should be controlled in a reasonable range.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to Nanjing Chenmao Corporation and Suzhou Fangdou Corporation for supplying the carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CFRE) tubes and aluminium foams. Also thankful to the school of science for the testing machine.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jacob GC, Fellers JF, Simunovic S, Starbuck JM, Energy absorption in polymer composites for automotive crashworthiness, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 36, 2002, pp, 813-850.
- [2] Farley GL, Energy absorption of composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 17, 1983, pp, 267-279.
- [3] Thornton PH, Energy absorption in composite structures, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 13, 1979, pp, 247-262.
- [4] Hamada H, Coppola JC, Hull D, Maekawa Z, Sato H, Comparison of energy absorption of carbon/E and carbon/PEEK composite tubes, *Composites*, 23, 1992, pp, 245-252.
- [5] Dubey DD, Vizzini JA, Energy absorption of composite plates and tubes, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 32, 1998, pp, 158-176.

- [6] Thornton PH, Harwood JJ, Beardmore P, Fibre reinforced plastic composites for energy absorption purposes, *Composites Science and Technology*, 24, 1985, pp, 275–298
- [7] Thornton PH, Edwards PJ, Energy absorption in composite tubes, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 16, 1982, pp, 521–545.
- [8] Mamalis AG, Yuan YB, Viegelaahn GL, Collapse of thin walled composite sections subjected to high speed axial loading, *International Journal of Vehicle Design*, 13, 1992, pp, 564–579.
- [9] Hull D, A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre reinforced composite tubes. *Composites Science and Technology*, 40, 1991, pp, 377–421.
- [10] Farley GL, Effect of specimen geometry on the energy absorption capability of composite materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 20, 1986, pp, 390–400.
- [11] Schmuesser DW, Wickliffe LE, Impact energy absorption of continuous fibre composite tubes, *Journal of Material Technology*, 109, 1987, pp, 72–77.
- [12] Cheng H, Huang X, Wei J, Han F, Damping capacity and compressive characteristic in some aluminum foams, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China*, 13, 2003, pp, 1046-1050.
- [13] Zhang C, Feng Y, Zhang X, Mechanical properties and energy absorption properties of aluminum foam-filled square tubes, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China*, 20, 2010, pp, 1380-1386
- [14] Liu Y, Gong X, Compressive behavior and energy absorption of metal porous polymer composite with interpenetrating network structure, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China*, 16, 2006, pp, 439-443.
- [15] Cheng H, Huang X, Xue G, Li J, Han F, Compressive deformation behavior and energy absorption characteristic of aluminum foam with elastic filler, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China*, 14, 2004, pp, 928-933.
- [16] Zhang H, Chen X, Fan X, Li Y, Compressive properties of aluminum foams by gas injection method, *Research and Development*, 9, 2012, pp, 215-220.
- [17] Wang Y, Zhai X, Dynamic Crushing Behaviors of Aluminum Foam Filled Energy Absorption Connectors, *International Journal of Steel Structures*, 19, 2019, pp, 241–254
- [18] Zhang H, Dou R, Zhao A, Zhu Z, Hu Y, Energy Absorption Property of Aluminum Foam Sandwich Panels Under Compression Load, *Trans Indian Inst Met*, 72, 2019, pp, 693–699.
- [19] J Kim, H Yoon, K Shin, A study on crushing behaviors of composite circular tubes with different reinforcing fibers, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 38, 2011, pp, 198-207.
- [20] MI Pinto, N DeNardo, A Shukla, Geometric impact on the implosion energy and failure mechanics of carbon composite tubes, *Multiscale and Multidisciplinary Modeling, Experiments and Design*, 1, 2018, pp, 171–179.
- [21] Liu Y, Gu H, Ren J, Wang X, Study on energy absorption capacity of carbon fiber tube, *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 199, 2018, pp, 32-76.
- [22] Jackson A, Dutton S, Gunnion AJ, Kelly D. Investigation into laminate design of open carbon-fibre/epoxy sections by quasi-static and dynamic crushing. *Compos Struct*, 93, 2011, :2646–54.
- [23] P.B. Ataabadia, D. Karagiozovab, M. Alves, Crushing and energy absorption mechanisms of carbon fiber-epoxy tubes under axial impact, *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 131, 2019, pp, 174–189.
- [24] A. Al Antali, R. Umer, J. Zhou, W.J. Cantwell, The energy-absorbing properties of composite tube-reinforced aluminum honeycomb, *Composite Structures*, 176, 2017, pp, 630–639.
- [25] R.A. Alia, W.J. Cantwell, G.S. Langdon, S.C.K. Yuen, G.N. Nurick, The energy-absorbing characteristics of composite tube-reinforced foam structures, *Composites: Part B*, 61, 2014, pp, 127–135.
- [26] J. Zhou, Z. Guan, W.J. Cantwell, The energy-absorbing behaviour of composite tube-reinforced foams, *Composites Part B*, 139, 2018, pp, 227–237.

- [27] Heimbs S. Energy absorption in aircraft structures, *Presented at the first international workshop on hydraulic equipment and support systems for mining IWHEM2012. Huludao, China; 2012*
- [28] Airoidi A, Bettini P, Zazzarini M, Scarpa F, Failure and energy absorption of plastic and composite chiral honeycombs. In: Schleyer G, Brebbia CA, editors, *Structures under Shock and Impact XII*, 2012. WIT Press; 2013. pp. 101-114.